

Experiences with the ENES System Software Stack: A Report about the workflow fit for the Extreme Scale Demonstrator (EsD)

Deliverable D3.8

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1. Abstract

In order to support the strategy of the European Commission towards developing exascale supercomputers based on competitive EU technology the deliverable discusses the requirements a workflow has to fulfil to keep its usability on the next generation hardware.

Yet, it is not clear whether we need a completely new concept for workflows or if it may be sufficient to adapt today's concepts to cope with future requirements. We expect that at least some components of workflows as they are in use today will stay more or less similar, e.g. the basic lifecycle of a model run should stay valid in general – even if the problem size will increase and thus impact the details.

Starting from this, we report on real life experiences when porting today's software stack needed to run Earth System Models to systems of different sizes by using the software tool SPACK. As a result, all supercomputers tested with our SPACK solution showed good and comprehensible practices in software stack configuration and maintenance. This result is expected to be beneficial not only for the weather and climate community, but also for other application fields that require exascale computing.

2. Conclusion & Results

1. We are aware, that problems with code portability will rise with the emergence of new architectures – in this way it is very hard to predict with certainty what the bottlenecks will be and how they can be solved. We think the best strategy to prepare the community is to provide and teach best practices in software development and software management.

2. The community has to be prepared to handle much more data. This will not be possible without the development of a more overarching understanding of the term “post-processing” as a summary of processes that makes the model output easier to perceive, interpret, store, transfer or use as an input for another post-processing procedure. Our suggestion is, that the community should invest more resources in the development of online data processing tools and use tools and concepts that work in a distributed way

3. In the future of exascale computing we will have to orchestrate a much higher number of nodes to get the scientific results. As a consequence, the community has to be prepared for increasing number of hardware failures and increasing complexity of internode communication. Thus developing strategies to increase fault tolerance may become a big issue.

The scientific community will struggle to face these challenges successfully without support of the industry, i.e. software and hardware vendors. Yet, the solutions offered by the industry might not be clear enough for the scientific community in terms of understand the complete end – to – end workflow in every detail. Interfaces need to be communicated more precisely and transparently and the best solution to avoid this problem is to decompose today's workflows into smaller, more independent steps, since those will be easier to change and easier to adapt.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes

Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The full report on the work done is provided in the annex to this document.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- Link to SPACK software for HPC <https://computation.llnl.gov/projects/spack-hpc-package-manager>
- ESIWACE deliverable D3.1 ESIWACE Application Software Framework: A White Paper.
- ESIWACE deliverable D3.5 How to Select, Configure and Install ESM Software Stacks
- ESIWACE deliverable D3.7 Software Stack for ESMs– A Specification narrowing down D3.5 for the demonstrators

All above deliverables are accessible here <https://www.esiwace.eu/results/deliverables>

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

This deliverable is in open access.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This deliverable is going to be made available in [Zenodo](#) for granting full access to communities beyond the ESIWACE community. Promotion of the deliverable will be done via the ESIWACE newsletter and mailing lists.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

All supercomputers tested with our SPACK solution showed good and comprehensible practices in software stack configuration and maintenance.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The deliverable directly benefits from findings of the previous ESIWACE deliverables D3.1, D3.5 and D3.7 and enlarges their focus by looking to future generation hardware and discusses the challenges connected to it. In this respect all ESIWACE work packages benefit from analysing the workflow.

Findings, issues and challenges of D3.8 are going to be an input for the successful bidders of the H2020 calls like INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 or INFRAEDI-02-2018. We are going to establish a link to the consortia coordinators via the DG Connect project officers, as soon as the successful projects are starting.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Number	Details	Total funding amount	Type of audience reached In the context of all dissemination & communication activities	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a workshop	1	Presentation of S. Kosukhin, Software stack deployment for ESM, ESIWACE and IS-ENES2 Joint final workshop on IS-ENES2 Workflow Solutions in Earth System Modelling and on Meta-Data Generation during Experiments, Costa da Caparica, 27-29 September 2016	See costs declared in form C of MPI-M	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry,	30
Participation to a conference	1	Presentation of K. Serradell (BSC) S. Kosukhin (MPI-M), Software stack deployment for Earth System Modelling using Spack, PRACE Days 2017 Barcelona, 15-18 May 2017	See costs declared in form C of MPI-M and BSC	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry	20
Publication of a report	1	Publication of the "Application Software Framework: A White Paper" on the website of the project https://www.esiwace.eu/results/misc/the-application-software-framework/view	See costs declared in form C of partners involved.	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry	
Participation to a workshop	1	Presentation of L. Kornblueh, S. Kosukhin, Spack for ICON; ICON Developers Meeting, 28.09.2017, Löwenstein	See costs declared in form C of MPI-M	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry	38
Participation to a workshop	1	Presentation of S. Kosukhin, Spack for ICON: Status Update, ICON Infrastructure Meeting, 09.02.2018, Karlsruhe	See costs declared in form C of MPI-M	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry	14
Organisation of a workshop (planned)	1	We have also submitted (not reviewed yet) an application to organize a tutorial "HPC Software Management with Spack" at ISC High Performance 2018, 24-28 June 2018, Frankfurt (https://www.isc-hpc.com/). Authors: M. Kuhn (Universität Hamburg), S. Kosukhin (Max Planck Institute for Meteorology), G. Becker (Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory), M. Culpo (EPFL).	See costs declared in form C of MPI-M	Scientific community, Higher education, Industry	

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.

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1. Introduction and Motivation

What is an Extreme Scale Demonstrator (EsD) and why does the EsD matter for workflow development?

In 2017 a number of European countries signed the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking¹, a legal entity that “will enable Member States to coordinate together with the Union their supercomputing strategies and investments” with the aim of:

- Acquiring and providing a world-class pre-exascale supercomputing infrastructure to Europe's scientific and industrial users, matching their demanding application requirements by 2020.
- Developing exascale supercomputers based on competitive EU technology that the Joint Undertaking could acquire around 2022-2023, and that would be ranking among the top three places in the world.

Moreover the Horizon2020 work programme for 2018 – 2020 call ICT-14-2019 requests to “demonstrate in operational environments the successful integration of technology building blocks developed in previous R&I actions into world-class Extreme Scale Demonstrators.” To reach this goal it will require a strong co-design approach driven by ambitious applications developed from scientific questions and engagement of technology suppliers.

In the following document, we indicate the requirements that a workflow has to fulfil to be able to operate on Extreme Scale Demonstrator (EsD) hardware and report on the first steps in the direction of enabling its usability on next generation systems.

What is a workflow?

Figure 1 drafts the life cycle of a workflow for weather and climate research as we experience it today. A scientific question initialises a processing and a data workflow, followed by a discussion in the scientific community analysing the results and then possibly a change in the model configuration or the scientific question.

Looking into the future, we expect the architecture of compute and storage hardware to become increasingly complex. With weather and climate models converging towards Earth-System models with even more complexity integrated into them, model development is turning into a highly challenging, long-term hardware/software co-design-driven software project. Thus it will no longer be possible to simply link and submit the code as is frequently the case today, but significantly more resource (computing time and storage space) has to be applied for (and then granted by computing centres); more libraries and software packages (with a possibly increasing number of interdependencies) have to be installed by system administrators and serviced by them; larger initial and boundary conditions have to be created and manipulated to fit specific requirements of the models or research questions. As a consequence, the models need to be configured and built ever more carefully in the context of specific future software and hardware developments.

When the model is running in production mode, the workflow has to cope with an increasing amount of output data (e.g. accumulated over a forecast day with a 10 km global model ~100 GB of 2D / 3D output data can be expected), that has to be written from temporary compute hardware storage to a space

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/eurohpc-joint-undertaking>

where the scientists have the possibility to evaluate and analyse the results.

Taken together, the post processing is becoming an increasingly complex task because most of the post processing tools available today are not able to operate in parallel – so the memory of single compute nodes on which the post processing job is running will very likely be insufficient to compute averages and time series from such huge data fields.

All these points have to be handled for projects using weather and climate models in general. When we now do the step from current petascale High Performance Computing (HPC) to future exascale HPC systems by using models with increasing resolution and physical complexity, the challenges will grow.

Fig.1: Cycle of Life of a workflow in weather and climate research

What will the ambitious applications from weather and climate research, that require an Extreme Scale Demonstrator (EsD) look like?

In the amendment to the ESiWACE proposal we announced *“atmosphere-only, ocean-only and coupled ocean-atmosphere simulations, which will be run at the highest affordable resolutions (target 1 km) to estimate the computability of configurations that will be sufficient to address key scientific challenges in weather and climate prediction.”* (ESiWACE Description of the Action, Part B)

One of the objectives of ESiWACE WP3 is to explicitly address the consequences resulting from this goal. In order to operate the application on the new EsD systems, the community has to *“reduce the skills gaps at individual centres by sharing best practice through worked examples using use-cases derived from user-driven engagement, the need to prepare extreme scale demonstrators, and governance”* (ESiWACE Description of the Action, Part B).

Do we need a special workflow to operate the EsD?

To date, it is not clear how the upcoming exascale hardware systems will look, but most experts assume that the basic structure of the extreme scale HPC will not substantially differ from that of an “ordinary” Tier0 / Tier 1 HPC system available nowadays, even if this is not the case in detail. Nevertheless, from this we conclude, that the principal requirements for the system software stack - in the sense that interdependencies of libraries and software packages have to be handled - will be similar, so it makes sense to extrapolate the findings from today regarding workflows and software stack design to future exascale systems.

1. What will be similar?

- The basic lifecycle (depicted in Fig.1) will still be valid in general – even when the increasing problem size will impact the details.
- Storage, versioning and Code maintenance will take place in central repositories (e.g. git / svn)
- Portability of codes and data (from machine to machine and architecture to architecture) will be essential – even when the portability of the codes will become more difficult.
- Performance portability will be an increasingly important issue
- Authentication and authorisation should be unified and (if possible) single sign on
- Error tracking will stay and probably become increasingly difficult (increasing with number of nodes / cores)

2. What will be different?

We expect that only very few exascale systems will be available world-wide within the next 5 years, with 1 – 2 systems hosted in Europe.

- The computer hardware might become more heterogeneous in future. If any of the exascale systems will work on GPU processors, the challenges regarding code, data and performance portability will increase.
 - Thus providing mechanisms to port code onto various kinds of hardware is even more important than it is today.
 - To guarantee that the models successful in use today can benefit from the hardware progress, serious restructuring of the code will be necessary.
- Significant increase of compute nodes will have serious consequences.
 - Mean time between failure will decrease significantly, with the requirement, that the workflow has to be extended to support automated and intelligent failure - restart procedures
 - To minimize resource costs for redundant computing
 - To be able to repeat individual time slices or retrieve additional variables at certain grid points on demand
 - Bit reproducibility will become increasingly difficult or impossible.
 - Evaluation paradigms will have to change (e.g. looking to average values / ensemble predictions / error bars instead on individual data / point of time).
- Resource costs for porting and testing of code to bigger hardware will grow but only few and well designed integration tests will be possible on the final system.
 - This requires a strategy to cope with: a possibility is to divide the code into blocks / dwarfs to enable separate testing on smaller hardware systems.
 - Increase concurrency of codes or at least parts of the codes will be important to make

the models scale on exascale systems. This can also be achieved via the dwarfs.

- More and faster hardware will result in more output data.
 - Restart data sets have to be written out more frequently to limit possible loss due to hardware failure.
 - As an alternative mechanism algorithmic approaches to fault tolerance may be considered
 - Only a well defined output data set (or variables averaged in time and / or space) can be written out
- Post processing tools show trends to be included into the model code to save compute time and resources for writing output and / or storing unnecessary raw data.
- Network complexity will increase quantitatively and qualitatively.
- Due to the increasing complexity it has to be expected, that the resulting solution of software and hardware interdependencies will no longer be transparent to the end users.

2. Results from previous Deliverables D3.1, D3.5 and D3.7

ESiWACE has the ambition to significantly improve the interaction between those with deep computing knowledge and those with the best scientific ideas. (See ESiWACE D3.1).

Deliverable D3.1 was a first attempt to conceptualize an Application Software Framework. The authors started the systematic discussion of the different steps needed to set up, run and evaluate a weather or climate system experiment. They do it with the focus on what has to be taken into account, when a summer school has to be organized.

Deliverable D3.5 then specifies a System Software Stack and delivers a kind of guideline / best practices for system administrators how to support it. The software stack consists of a collection of packages and tools required by most ESM workflows in Europe and taken together enables the performance of a summer school on Earth System Modelling, which took place in summer 2016 (3rd E2SCMS, European Earth System and Climate Modelling School) in Helsinki, a PRACE Tier1 centre.

On top of the collection and description of software, the authors recommended the use of a tool named SPACK that simplifies installation and portability of libraries, tools and software that need to be assembled for a specific workflow. They end with an outlook on user feedback to evaluate the practicability of this tool.

Deliverable D3.7 then reported on the steps needed to adapt the identified System Software Stack to enable its operation on an anticipated EsD. Therefore, they collected the software and tools that will be needed for the atmosphere and ocean models selected to become parts of an application for an EsD. They compared the list with the one from developed in D3.5 and they found impressive overlaps. As a result, the authors again gave space to advertise the SPACK tool and presented the advantages. They concluded that SPACK would reduce the complexity task of installing software, managing dependencies, compilers and modules. Nevertheless, they emphasised, that not all software needed to build a workflow to enable model runs on an anticipated EsD could be automatically installed by SPACK as long as it is not part of the supported SPACK software stack (<https://spack.io>).

3. What does it mean for experiments on future EsD hardware?

As agreed in the description of the action after the first project review, ESIWACE will deliver a feasibility study for community models run at global high-resolution. This study should then result in a roadmap to guide the community towards the development of community models for pre-exascale and exascale systems, e.g. the EsDs.

This roadmap will be realised in two steps:

Step 1: Very high-resolution atmosphere-only and ocean-only demonstrators

Step 2: High resolution coupled atmosphere-ocean demonstrators

The applications will be based on following models:

Step 1²:

- IFS: Integrated Forecast System (developed by ECMWF) [D2.8, PM24].
- ICON: Icosahedral non-hydrostatic general circulation model (developed by DWD, MPI-M and DKRZ) [D2.9, PM24].
- NEMO: Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (developed by IPSL) [D2.10, PM42].

Step 2:

- EC-Earth: European consortium developing a coupled climate model. The configuration analysed uses IFS for atmosphere, NEMO for ocean and OASIS for coupling [D2.11, PM42].
- ICON: as coupled climate model using its own ocean component ICON-OCE and the YAC coupler. [D2.12, PM42].

What has to be done to make the workflow EsD – ready?

Starting from the conclusions of deliverables 3.1, 3.5 and 3.7 we report on experiences on the following different Tier0 / Tier1 / Tier2 environments using the models IFS and ICON available from of Step 1

- MISTRAL (Tier1@DKRZ)
- Mare Nostrum (Tier0@BSC)
- Marconi (Tier0@CMCC)
- Archer (Tier1@NCAS)
- Desktops and laptops with different Linux distributions

In this section we first introduce some details on real application experiences for the hi-res case because this is basically the most important input to the overall workflow, and then we discuss the workflow and package portability issue.

1. Report on real application experiences at BSC

BSC plans to run the T1279-ORCA12 EC-Earth ensemble configuration in EsD in production. For that, the EC-Earth model will run in a minimal throughput for climate runs, producing a reduced set of outputs (with enough variables for science production) and setting up a post-process task producing data ready to be analysed by scientists. All these steps should be performed in a decent amount of time.

Challenges:

Although we are building our framework solutions to be able to run such configuration, some issues

² In brackets are indicated the Project –month (PM) and Deliverables numbers (D) to report on implementation and performance analysis.

persist. The current throughput is still insufficient to produce results and our online model post-process capabilities are not yet fully developed to avoid saving a huge amount of data before post-processing. And last but not least, our analysing tools are not yet adapted to deal with the large amount of memory needed to work with such resolution.

How to tackle these different challenges?

For the performance issue, BSC is working on analysing codes in different HPC machines, using performance tools to detect bottlenecks and improve the efficiency of the codes. Different architectures and programming models are tested to be ready to port the climate model to the final architecture chosen for the EsD. Related to online post-processing of the model, a project to port XIOS I/O server to EC-Earth will improve I/O management in the atmospheric model and will allow us to perform more complex diagnostics. This will reduce the size of the output produced without losing crucial data for the following stage. And finally, to improve post-processing tasks, different tools are being modified to be able to work by chunks, reducing the size of the memory needed to perform the analysis.

2. Experiences with installation of software stack on different platforms with SPACK

Our tests included installations of the software stack as described in the handbook for system administrators.

Main challenges:

1. To employ the full potential of SPACK a relatively new implementation of the environment modules has to be available on the computer. Usually the implementation of the correct environment modules is done automatically by SPACK, but the problem then can be, that this version won't become the version the system administrators maintain. Thus, our experience was, that in several cases either unsupported versions (in the sense of too old) of the Environment Modules were maintained at the computers or non-standard approaches of the configuration were found. The consequence was that the installation broke the Python interface of the Environment Modules and thus the usability of SPACK decreased significantly. To overcome this issue, additional configuration efforts were required. Since updating and reconfiguration of the Environment Modules was not always possible – or at least required a lot of time – we extended SPACK to also support older versions of Environment Modules to keep SPACK's level of usability.
2. Intel compilers can't work without the GNU compiler collection and GNU Binutils on Linux systems. The scenarios of interaction between them depend on a particular use case. Usually not all interaction scenarios required to build the software stack are tested and covered during the installation and configuration of the Intel compilers – as a consequence, not all the required environment variables are set properly by the corresponding environment modules.
3. By implementation of additional features into SPACK, SPACK's functionality was extended to compensate for the deficiencies in the configuration of compiler toolchains. By working with Intel compilers, we learned, that our solution is general enough to help with problems associated with other compilers. To be more specific: the newly implemented feature let users specify which additional environment modifications must be undertaken before running a particular compiler.
4. The implementation and use of SPACK helped us to find various inaccuracies and undocumented features in related software. They were documented and reported to the respective development teams. Meanwhile workarounds were implemented into SPACKS's installation recipes.

4. Recommendations and Conclusions

We reported our experiences with testing the software deployment system on the whole bandwidth of different types and sizes of compute systems. We think, only real hands-on experience on many different software environments can provide the needed input for achieving the goals and increasing the usability of the workflow. This experience, together with the feedback from the community can prompt us into the direction of further development of the living documents.

Recommendations for the software stack

All supercomputers tested with our SPACK solution showed good and comprehensible practices in software stack configuration and maintenance. This result is expected to be beneficial not only for the weather and climate community, but also for other application fields that require exascale computing. We understand that updates and changes of supercomputing environments can't be rapid, but employing standardized practices and getting rid of arguable software and procedures are necessary to stay successful in the long run.

Thus, we mention two goals for the future:

- Development of recommendations for users and system administrators, which might eliminate the excessive heterogeneity of the software environments in the future;
- Providing users with a tool for software deployment that is flexible enough to overcome flaws in the existing software environments.

Conclusions

1. We are aware, that problems with code portability will rise with the emergence of new architectures – in this way it is very hard to predict with certainty what the bottlenecks will be and how they can be solved. We think the best strategy to prepare the community is to provide and teach best practices in software development and software management.

2. The community has to be prepared to handle much more data. This will not be possible without the development of a more overarching understanding of the term “post-processing” as a summary of processes that makes the model output easier to perceive, interpret, store, transfer or use as an input for another post-processing procedure. Our suggestion is, that the community should invest more resources in the development of online data processing tools and use tools and concepts that work in a distributed way

3. In the future of exascale computing we will have to orchestrate a much higher number of nodes to get the scientific results. As a consequence, the community has to be prepared for increasing number of hardware failures and increasing complexity of internode communication. Thus developing strategies to increase fault tolerance may become a big issue.

The scientific community will struggle to face these challenges successfully without support of the industry, i.e. software and hardware vendors. Yet, the solutions offered by the industry might not be clear enough for the scientific community in terms of understand the complete end – to – end workflow in every detail. Interfaces need to be communicated more precisely and transparently and the best solution to avoid this problem is to decompose today's workflows into smaller, more independent steps, since those will be easier to change and easier to adapt.

5. Glossary

Dwarf	Encapsulated fundamental algorithmic building blocks in ESMs
ESM	Earth System models
ENES	European Network for Earth System Modelling
EsD	Extreme Scale Demonstrator
E2SCMS	European Earth System and Climate Modelling School
GIT	Open Source versioning system
HPC	High Performance Computing
PM	Project Month
SVN	Subversion

6. References (*Bibliography*)

- ESIWACE deliverable D3.1 ESIWACE Application Software Framework: A White Paper.
- ESIWACE deliverable D3.5 How to Select, Configure and Install ESM Software Stacks
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